

Aleksandra Mitrović,*
Teaching Assistant,
Faculty of Law, University of Priština,
Head Office in Kosovska Mitrovica,
Republic of Serbia

UDK: 349.2:347.9(497.11)
UDK: 339.109.6(497.11)

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17951218

COLLECTIVE LABOUR DISPUTE AS A TYPE OF SOCIAL CONFLICT AND ITS RESOLUTION**

Abstract: *This scientific paper aims to explore the sociological and legal framework of peaceful resolution of collective labour disputes, present experiences in resolving collective labour disputes as a type of social conflict in a society, specifically in the Republic of Serbia, and thus confirm the advantages in the work of the Agency for Peaceful Settlement of Labour Disputes as a state institution facing modern social challenges in approaching the EU concept, where social peace is the basis for harmonising domestic and European labour legislation. Prior Agency experience proves that the agency method of resolving collective labour disputes is an extraordinary and more efficient way of protecting the employees' rights. Due to tardiness, legalism, formalism and high financial costs, regular court proceedings cannot meet expectations in the field of labour disputes, nor can they be a solution for resolving social conflict ultimately aimed at establishing social peace.*

Keywords: *labour dispute, social conflict, collective labour dispute, peaceful resolution of labour disputes, Agency, social peace, social dialogue.*

1. Collective Labor Dispute as a Type of Social Conflict

A collective labour dispute as a social phenomenon is normatively shaped. The essence of a labour dispute lies in the social conflict that occurs as a

* aleksandra.mitrovic@pr.ac.rs, ORCID ID 0000-0003-1150-6907.

** The paper was presented at the International Scientific Conference Law and Social Conflicts, held at the Faculty of Law, University of Niš, on 25 and 26 April 2025.

result of the differing interests of social partners (the employer and an employee). Such conflicts are an inevitable result of social cohesion, emerging from constant social interactions imposed by the existential conditions of life. The social aspect is a new dimension in studying the collective labour dispute as a legal phenomenon with a social character, or as a social phenomenon with a normative form. In that regard, the collective labour dispute is perceived by relying on its two essential elements: 1) its essence – the conflict of interests as part of the social context; and 2) its structure – a legally regulated institution. It also entails a generalised systematisation of the nature of a labour dispute as a concept, as it is impossible to make any attempt of a more precise systematisation. The reason lies in the complex nature of the labour dispute phenomenon as a type of (undesirable) social relation because social relations intrinsically carry the essential characteristic of *ars inventoriae*, which implies that new topoi are constantly created while the existing ones are modified (Visković, 1997: 83).

When the focus is shifted to social relations and when law is conceived as an exclusively social phenomenon, social relations become the materialised substrate of law, including those that create negative effects, such as social conflicts (like collective labour disputes). We can, therefore, conclude that law is influenced by social existence, and that in this respect, it is autonomous and formalised through legal norms. Social relations, values, and norms are the components (elements) of law, while at the same time being the sources of law; thus, social relations are the material sources of law, legal values are the axiological (ethical) sources of law, while legal norms are the formal sources of law (Visković, 1981: 83).

Given that labour disputes fall into the category of particularly undesirable social conflicts, in order to successfully approach their resolution, mitigation, or prevention, it is necessary to approach the problem radically. Here, the term “radically” means addressing it “root-and-branch”, i.e. beginning from the “heart of the matter” in order to better understand the concept of a labour dispute. The theory of hermeneutics (the art of understanding and interpretation) claims that in order to interpret something we must first understand it. Therefore, understanding is considered the fundamental phenomenon of all relations among people and of man’s relation to everything that exists, and is thus referred to as the primordial phenomenon (Urbaničić, et al., 1973: 433). Social phenomena are manifested, *inter alia*, as “processes of communication or exchange of information, processes in which people send each other messages with the intent to show, describe, explain, ask, inquire, convey emotions, create factual situations, etc.” (Visković, 1981: 370). From this standpoint, the study approaches labour disputes from a

socio-legal perspective, which manages to track the variability of social relations while simultaneously contributing to the restoration of the meaning of legal norms governing those relations (Visković, 1989: 144-167).

After all, law is “a system of state and social norms that formally regulate the most important and most conflicting interpersonal relations in order to achieve peace, security, justice, and other socially dominant values” (Visković, 2001: 117). Therefore, the structure of a legal norm will not be defined by a logical concept but rather by the needs, the balance of power, and the goals (interests) of society. Social practice has shown that social conflicts are costly for all social actors (the state, employers, and employees). It has driven the pursuit for more effective strategies and mechanisms for maintaining social peace. Court proceedings involve high costs, and taking legal action in court is unattainable for many employees. Another reason for avoiding judicial proceedings is that labour disputes often take many years due to ever-present formalism; thus, “(...) justice, if it is too slow, becomes pointless(...)”, which causes frustration among employees (Bronstein, 1990: 67). The duration and inefficiency of court proceedings can be best illustrated by some statistical data: out of 14 judgments of the ECtHR delivered in 2012, the Court found a violation of the right to a trial within a reasonable time in as many as 11 cases. The ECtHR jurisprudence¹ has shown that, out of 61 judgments delivered in cases against the Republic of Serbia, a violation of the applicant’s rights was established in 54 cases, most often a violation of the right to a trial within a reasonable time. It has been noted that the observed problems, such as a *high unemployment rate, the existence of a widespread informal labour market, and the weak capacity of the competent government authorities (labour inspection)* in Serbia, work in favour of unscrupulous employers. The low rate of unionisation among employers in the private sector negatively affects employees in their decision to resolve their disputes in court. High unemployment and the widespread informal employment, together with the weak capacity of the competent government authorities (labour inspections), deter employees from attempting to settle their disputes with employers in court.

The European Economic and Social Committee believes that “social dialogue should be regular and structural in nature” rather than being held *ad hoc* only when needed, and that “it should be more effective and result-driven”

¹ ECtHR Case 57611/10 *Anđelić and Others v The Republic of Serbia* [2013], Report of the Representative of the Republic of Serbia before the European Court of Human Rights, Available 12 January 2018; http://www.zastupnik.gov.rs/uploads/cr/presude/u-odnosu-na-rs/presuda-andjelic-i-dr-protiv-srbije-p.-br.-57611-10/andjelic_idr_p_57611_10_ser.pdf.

(Sibian, Leihner, 2013: 4). In order to establish and preserve such a socio-labour climate, the state has to institute adequate instruments for the peaceful settlement of labour disputes. Consequently, in 2004, the National Assembly of Serbia adopted the Act on the Peaceful Settlement of Labour Disputes (hereinafter: the PSLD Act, 2004),² which envisaged the establishment of the National Agency for the Peaceful Settlement of Labour Disputes as the operational body for the implementation of this Act.

2. Efficiency of Agency-based Settlement and Inefficiency of Judicial Resolution of Collective Labor Disputes

In addition to the classical form of mediation as a method of resolving collective labour disputes, a new model introduced in Sweden in 1990 also deserves to be mentioned; it is called the “Mediator of Realm”, which may be translated as “State Mediator”. The state mediator operates at the national level and represents a kind of super mediator, while also playing the role of a good host of the state (*bonus pater patrie*) (Fahlbeck, 1991: 418). By analogy, the National Agency for the Peaceful Settlement of Labour Disputes in the Republic of Serbia (hereinafter: PSLD Agency) is assigned the role of the state mediator, and accordingly, one of its goals is to mediate an agreement between the conflicting parties.

The advantage of mediation lies in its tripartite foundation, where out-of-court bodies resolve labour disputes with minimum formalities, thus making the procedure less costly than court proceedings while the parties retain their autonomy and focus on developing good relations between social partners in the future. Thus, mediation “can be a therapy for treating current disorders in the relations between an employer and employees, as well as for preventing new ones” (Kostić, Perić, 2009: 217). The advantages of settling labour disputes before the Agency include:

- Speed of labour dispute resolution: under the law, the time limit for resolving a dispute is 30 days. The parties shall receive a final and enforceable decision within one month from the opening of the hearing (Art. 36 PSLD Act). A collective dispute is resolved without unnecessary delays, with the assistance of a conciliator jointly chosen by the parties (management and trade unions), thus ensuring equality for all parties. The expertise and experience of an impartial conciliator contribute to

² Zakon o mirnom rešavanju radnih sporova (Act on Peaceful Settlement of Labour Disputes), *Službeni glasnik Republike Srbije*, br. 125/04, 104/09 i 50/18 (hereinafter: the PSLD Act).

the development, improvement, and tolerance of social dialogue, thereby avoiding the most harmful and costly consequence – a strike;

- Simplicity of initiating and conducting the labour dispute: it is sufficient to fill in a form available at the Agency's website and send it to the Agency;
- Cost-effectiveness: the procedure is completely free, saving both parties time and money. In individual disputes, which can last for years due to overloaded courts, an employee may face an increasingly difficult financial position during lengthy proceedings, while employers face growing costs for damages due to lost profit resulting from unlawful dismissal and accrued interest on unpaid salaries. In collective disputes, burdened by transition issues (privatisation and restructuring of the economy, accompanied by the low level of economic democracy and tolerance), the mediator helps the parties find a solution which would be acceptable to both the employer and the employees;
- Reduced court caseload;

Increased trust between social partners: the mediator's assistance enables the parties to reach a compromise and functional solution, in line with the modern EU concept of peaceful resolution of labour disputes.

The inefficiency of court proceedings actually confirms the Agency efficiency because through mediation, the Agency demonstrates its advantages over the shortcomings of the classical judicial process. The total number of initiated labour disputes (6,920) in the period 2015–2021 shows that the results of agency-based mediation have been accepted with increasing trust by the citizens of the Republic of Serbia. It is clearly reflected in the trend dynamics of the total number of peacefully resolved labour disputes (4,380), a large number of which were resolved on the merits (2,925), including a significant number of individual labour disputes resolved on merits (2,870) and collective labour disputes resolved on merits (55) in the period from 1 Jan 2018 to 31 Dec 2021. A slightly increasing trend can also be observed in the total number of peacefully resolved disputes in both cases: in peacefully resolved individual and collective labour disputes (PSLD Agency, 2021: 26-28).³

³ The data have been compiled from the Republic Agency for the Peaceful Settlement of Labour Disputes. Republička agencija za mirno rešavanje radnih sporova (2021). *Informator o radu* (Bulletin, National Agency for Peaceful Settlement of Labor Disputes of the RS), RAZMRRS, Beograd, 2021. <https://www.ramrrs.gov.rs/storage/documents/Gx8DsL5PIBLanhLMSNiReaU20sGQAAHX8qDVY1ev.pdf> (For more information on the period 2015-2021, see: PSLD Agency, 2021:26-28).

Indicators of (in)efficiency refer to the *number of unresolved cases, the length of judicial proceedings* which, according to European standards, also includes the *enforcement procedure, the costs of the judiciary, and the level of respect for human rights*. The large number of unresolved cases in the courts of the Republic of Serbia, the high percentage of outdated unresolved cases, and especially the backlog of old unresolved enforcement cases, require comprehensive and long-term measures to be undertaken at the national level. Practice in our country shows that the issue of judicial efficiency in Serbia is one of the central areas in the negotiations for Chapter 23 of the EU accession.

The emerging problem is the *violation of fundamental human rights* in the domain of legal protection because the enforcement procedure in about 100,000 court cases in the Republic of Serbia has lasted for more than 10 years. On the other hand, the procedure before the Agency is completed in only one month. *Cost-effectiveness* is also one of the many advantages of agency-based dispute resolution, as the entire procedure is free of charge and very simple to initiate. The savings achieved by the Agency for the state, solely in resolving individual labor disputes during the first five years of its work, amounted to between €3,000 and €5,000. In the private sector, a collective labour dispute saves between €400,000 and €500,000 for a single day of a prevented strike in a large enterprise. The procedure can be initiated *without formalities* and may be brought before a mediator or arbitrator, depending on whether it is an individual or collective labour dispute. This further highlights another advantage of agency-based resolution: *flexibility*, which implies the freedom of social partners to choose the method by which they will resolve the existing conflict. Therefore, “(...) a visible direct proportion exists between the success and efficiency of the transition process, i.e. political, economic, and social reforms, and social peace and the development of social dialogue as one of the means to achieve such social peace” (Marinković, 2010: 297).

The PSLD Agency has achieved remarkable results and become a leader in the region. Its importance is confirmed on a daily basis not only in the formal and legal sense but also in the field of social practice. Since its establishment in 2005 until the end of 2016, a total of 14,192 labour disputes were initiated before the Agency, including 5,118 individual disputes resolved on the merits and 126 collective labour disputes also resolved on the merits.⁴ It can be concluded that the situation in the field of peaceful settlement of labour

⁴ Republička agencija za mirno rešavanje radnih sporova/PSLD Agency (2018). *Priručnik o dobrim praksama u mirnom rešavanju radnih sporova* (Handbook of Good Practices in Peaceful Settlement of Labour Disputes, Lazović, I (ed.), RAMRRS, Beograd; <https://www.ramrrs.gov>.

disputes in the Republic of Serbia, and the contribution of the PSLD Agency after more than a decade of work and the implementation of the Act on Peaceful Settlement of Labour Disputes, is satisfactory and encouraging, with evident progress in all segments (PSLD Agency, 2018: 37).

The Agency encourages social partners to sit at the negotiating table, peacefully reconcile and find mutually satisfactory solutions. Furthermore, it strives to resolve as many collective labour disputes as possible through mediation, i.e. by extrajudicial means, and thus contribute to reducing conflict-based methods and strikes. If a strike in a major company were to be reduced for just one day through Agency mediation, it would affect the Agency's budget for the following three years. Moreover, if the Agency could mediate in reaching a solution even before the strike began, the savings would be immeasurable, and an expert in the economic-financial field would have to adequately assess and explain them.

Thus, the PSLG Agency contributes to establishing and preserving industrial and social peace, as well as ensuring social security within a stabilised financial framework. In turn, its activities relieve the judiciary of labour disputes' caseload. Social peace, by definition, constitutes a part of the overall social peace and stability of a country and reflects the relationships among social partners: political authorities, trade unions, and employers. In line with the principle of interconnected vessels, social peace can function only as part of the overall political, economic, and social stability of society (Pochet, Fajertag, 2000: 9-40).

3. Social Dialogue as a Guarantor of Social Peace

The foundation for resolving collective labour disputes rests on the prevention of conflict and maintenance or establishment of social dialogue. The essence lies not in the mere formal fulfilment of social dialogue but in the effective harmonisation of the social partners' positions. Hence, it has been emphasised that negotiations to resolve conflicts in the field of labour should not be understood by trade unions and employers as a fight of gladiators, as was often the case in the past, but rather as an attempt to find a middle ground that will satisfy the interests of both parties. Employers' and workers' organisations have the role of social partners, which should actively participate in the formulation, adoption, supervision, and implementation of international labour standards as they are defined by the Inter-

rs/images/Prirucnik-o-dobrim-praksama.pdf (For more information on the period 2005-2016, see: PSLD Agency, 2018: 28-29).

national Labour Organization (ILO). The ILO functions as a tripartite body and enables employers' organisations, workers' organisations, and governments to have a voice as equal social partners in creating labour standards, policies, and programmes in the field of work. Social policy formulated through dialogue between social partners has the best chance of achieving the goals agreed upon by the international community. ILO standards establish the framework for shaping social policy that promotes economic development and ensures the well-being of all who implement them.

International labour law insists on the existence and maintenance of social dialogue, i.e. cooperation between the state, employers, and employees in carrying out certain labour-related activities. The European Economic and Social Committee stresses the importance of social dialogue and "calls upon all stakeholders to make the best possible use of existing institutions, particularly the Social and Economic Council (SEC). It calls upon the government to continue to promote the SEC, to consult it more systematically on all policies in which workers have a legitimate interest. The European Economic and Social Committee considers that social dialogue should be regular and structural in nature, rather than *ad hoc*, and that it should be more effective and result-driven" (EESC, 2013).⁵ Only when social partners are equal in dialogue can we speak of a systemic shift in resolving labour disputes, i.e. systemic changes which will also achieve, through social cohesion, the goal of social dialogue: the preservation and stabilisation of labour and social peace.

Labour legislation as a whole should serve this purpose by providing incentives to create an adequate social climate that would accumulate through the establishment of social balance between the social partners. The establishment of such balance between social partners, i.e. the legitimate protection of employees' and employers' interests is a fundamental condition for social peace and prosperity. Naturally, to establish and sustain such a social and labour climate, the state must put in place adequate instruments of social peace, i.e. appropriate methods of peaceful resolution of labour disputes.

Such methods have been successfully applied by the PSLD Agency in the Republic of Serbia. According to the latest results, a total of 1,215 motions for labour dispute resolution were filed with the Agency in 2022, while 975 motions were filed in 2023 (PSLD Agency, 2023:11).⁶ Research indicates that

⁵ European Economic and Social Committee/EESC (2013). Opinion of the European Economic and Social Committee on 'The role of civil society in EU-Serbia relations', 2013/C 327/02, 491st plenary session held on 10-11 July 2013, *Official Journal of the EU*, 12.11.2013, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=OJ:C:2013:327:FULL>.

⁶ Republička agencija za mirno rešavanje radnih sporova/PSLD Agency (2023).

the Agency provided its services within the prescribed period in 975 cases; no cases were recorded on providing services after the expiry of the prescribed period. These facts clearly demonstrate the PSLD Agency's efficiency.

4. Conclusion

Conflicts, disagreements or disputes in the field of labour arise as a catalyst for change in that area. The consequences of labour disputes resolved in court proceedings served as the initial trigger for seeking new, extrajudicial, and consensual methods of dispute resolution. Since social conflicts have proven costly for the state and society in general, the search for strategies and mechanisms of social peace has led to the emergence of new institutions of social partnership that serve the purpose of peaceful settlement of labour disputes.

In the Republic of Serbia, the National Agency for Peaceful Settlement of Labour Disputes was established in order to create social balance between the legitimate interests of employees and employers, but also to contribute to the harmonisation of the national legislation with EU labour legislation. Research results confirm that the PSLD Agency functions as an efficient, cost-effective, and neutral mediator, established by the state to safeguard social peace and cohesion. By fostering greater trust among social partners, the Agency has succeeded in cultivating a more favourable social climate, as evidenced in the significant reduction in strikes, which is one of the strategic objectives for maintaining social peace and well-being as key values of the European concept. The findings of this study support the hypothesis that the PSLD Agency safeguards the workers' rights more effectively through the mediation-based peaceful settlement of collective labour disputes. It is clearly evidenced in the growing frequency of employing this institute in resolving labour disputes between social partners.

References

Bronstein, A. S. (1990). Le protection contre le licenciement injustifié en Amérique Latine. *Revue internationale du travail*. Vol. 129(5). Genève: Bureau international du Travail. 655-674.

INFORMACIJA Socijalno-ekonomskom savetu Republike Srbije u vezi sa podacima o kojima se vode evidencije i drugim pitanjima od značaja za postupke mirnog rešavanja radnih sporova za 2022. god. (Information to the Socio-Economic Council RS on recorded data concerning proceedings for peaceful settlement of labour disputes for 2022), RAMRRS, Beograd; <https://www.ramrrs.gov.rs/storage/documents/3bZVhVWZd7j1Z3bQqfkF7ptiEuOw-ISageB40U6Ku.pdf>.

Fahlbeck, R. (1991). Les modalités de règlement des conflits collectifs d'intérêts. *Raport National Suede*. XIII Congrès Mondial de Droit du Travail et de la Sécurité Sociale, Athens; Genève: Bureau international du Travail. 418.

Kostić, D., Perić, V. J. (2009). Optimalni uslovi za mirenje u kolektivnim radnim sporovima (Optimal conditions for mediation in collective labor disputes), *Socijalna prava i ekonomska kriza*, Zbornik radova sa Savetovanja pravnika "Zlatiborski pravnički dani", Zlatibor; Udruženje za radno pravo i socijalno osiguranje Srbije, Intermex, Beograd, 2009 (217).

Маринковић, Д., Маринковић, В. (2010). Пут Србије ка европском социјалном моделу–стање и перспективе (Serbia's path towards the European social model: status and prospects), *Остваривање и заштита социјалних права – Златибор 2010*, Зборник Удружења за радно право и социјално осигурање Србије, Интермекс, Београд, 282-298.

Pochet, P., Fajertag, G. (2000). A New Era for Social Pacts in Europe. In: Pochet, P. Fajertag, G.(eds.). *Social Pacts in Europe: New Dynamics*. Brussels: ETUI, OSE. 9-40.

Republička agencija za mirno rešavanje radnih sporova/PSLD Agency (2021). *Informator o radu* (Bulletin, National Agency for Peaceful Settlement of Labor Disputes), RAMRRS, Beograd. <https://www.ramrrs.gov.rs/storage/documents/Gx8DsL5PIBLanhLMSNiReaU20sGQAAHX8qDVY1ev.pdf>

Republička agencija za mirno rešavanje radnih sporova/PSLD Agency (2018). *Priručnik o dobrim praksama u mirnom rešavanju radnih sporova* (Handbook of Good Practices in Peaceful Settlement of Labour Disputes), Lazović, I (ed.), RAMRRS, Beograd; <https://www.ramrrs.gov.rs/images/Prirucnik-o-dobrim-praksama.pdf>

Republička agencija za mirno rešavanje radnih sporova/PSLD Agency (2023). INFORMACIJA Socijalno-ekonomskom savetu Republike Srbije u vezi sa podacima o kojima se vode evidencije i drugim pitanjima od značaja za postupke mirnog rešavanja radnih sporova za 2022. god. (Information to the Socio-Economic Council RS on recorded data concerning proceedings for peaceful settlement of labour disputes for 2022), RAMRRS, Beograd; <https://www.ramrrs.gov.rs/storage/documents/3bZVhVWzd7j1Z3bQqfkF7ptiEuOwISageB40U6Ku.pdf>

Sibian, I., Leihner, C. (2013). *The Role of civil society in EU - Serbia relations*, REX/381-EESC-2013-1176, Brussels: European Economic and Social Committee, <https://www.eesc.europa.eu/en/our-work/opinions-information-reports/opinions/role-civil-society-eu-serbia-relations>

Urbaničić, I., et al. (1973). *Hermeneutika: teorija tumačenja i razumevanja* (Hermeneutics: interpretation and understanding theory), *Časopis Delo* 4/5, Biblioteka Argumenti, Knjiga 19, Beograd: NOLIT (1973), 433

Visković, N. (1997). *Argumentacija i pravo* (Argumentation and Law). Split: Pravni fakultet.

Visković, N. (1981). O tumačenju pravnih akata (On the Interpretation of legal acts), *Zbornik radova Pravnog fakulteta u Zagrebu*. Zagreb: Pravni fakultet. 3-4/1981. 370.

Visković, N. (1981). *Pojam prava. Prilog integralnoj teoriji prava* (The concept of law: a contribution to the integral theory of law), Split: Pravni fakultet

Visković, N. (1989). *Tumačenje u pravu. Jezik prava*. (Interpretation in law: the language of law), Zagreb: Naprijed. 144-167.

Visković, N. (2001). *Teorija države i prava* (Theory of state and law), Zagreb: Birotehnika CDO

Legal documents

European Economic and Social Committee/EESC (2013). Opinion of the European Economic and Social Committee on 'The role of civil society in EU-Serbia relations', 2013/C 327/02, EU, *Official Journal*, 12.11.2013, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=OJ:C:2013:327:FULL>

Zakono o mirnom rešavanju radnih sporova (Act on Peaceful Settlement of Labour Disputes, PSLD Act), *Službeni glasnik Republike Srbije*, br. 125/04, 104/09 i 50/18; https://www.paragraf.rs/propisi/zakon_o_mirnom_resavanju_radnih_sporova.html

Judicial practice

ECtHR Case 57611/10 *Anđelić and Others v The Republic of Serbia* [2013] ECHR Strasbourg; Report of the Representative of the Republic of Serbia before the ECtHR, retrieved 12 January 2018 from http://www.zastupnik.gov.rs/uploads/cr/presude/u-odnosu-na-rs/presuda-andjelic-i-dr.-protiv-srbije-p.-br.-57611-10/andjelic_idr_p_57611_10_ser.pdf

Александра Митровић,
Асистент,
Правни факултет, Универзитет у Приштини
са привременим седиштем у Косовској Митровици,
Република Србија

КОЛЕКТИВНИ РАДНИ СПОР КАО ВИД ДРУШТВЕНОГ КОНФЛИКТА И ЊЕГОВО РЕШАВАЊЕ

Резиме

Овај научни рад има за циљ да истражи социолошко-правни оквир мирног решавања колективних радних спорова, прикаже искуства у решавању колективног радног спора као вида друштвеног конфликта у једном друштву, конкретно Републици Србији и тиме потврди предности у раду Агенције за мирно решавање радних спорова као државне институције, пред савременим друштвеним изазовима у приближавању концепту ЕУ, где је социјални мир основа за хармонизацију домаћег и европског радног законодавства. Искуство у раду Агенције за мирно решавање радних спорова доказује да је агенцијски метод решавања колективних радних спорова, као ванредни, а уједно и ефикаснији начин заштите права радника – запослених, будући да редовно судско решавање услед спорости, легализма, формализма и високих финансијских издатака, не може испунити очекивања из области радних спорова, нити бити решење за разрешење друштвеног конфликта које има за циљ успостављање социјалног мира.

Кључне речи: радни спор, друштвени конфликт, колективни радни спор, Агенција, мирно решавање радних спорова, социјални мир, социјални дијалог.

СЕСИЈА ЗА МЕЂУНАРОДНО ПРАВО

INTERNATIONAL LAW SESSION

